

ISLAMIC AZAD UNIVERSITY
SOUTH TEHRAN BRANCH
FACULTY OF TECHNICAL AND ENGINEERING
DEPARTMENT OF SOFTWARE ENGINEERING
”M.Sc” THESIS

SUBJECT:

**Building Agile Model for Local Server to Cloud Data
Communication Improvement**

THESIS ADVISOR:

Najma malekmohammadi / Ph.D

CONSULTING ADVISOR:

Ali brmaandina / Ph.D

BY:

Hussam Khalil khudear

November 2022

1. Abstract

In today's IT world, combining agile development and cloud computing is a great way to effectively meet customer needs. Both cloud and agile contribute to improving cloud computing opportunities through the rapid development of iterative software versions so that they require feedback and reduce costs (Ambreen, Ayesha, & Muhammad, 2013)

Analyze this study .The processes and benefits of the Agile methodology and issues related to cloud computing promote greater levels of innovation, allow needs to be discovered and verified. (Addicam.V.Sanjay, 2020)

Agile development methodologies and cloud computing both go hand in hand with each other nicely, agile cloud development is the most modern succession in practice as when rapid development and cloud computing are integrated withy bring the investigation of new technologies and tools. (Kannan, 2012)

With the development of technologies provided by the web and the acceleration of the flow of data available to users, many companies and institutions have tended to provide their applications via the Internet using a technology known as cloud computing. It also gives the beneficiary the ability to store, process, transmit and share information (from anywhere and at any time) as these services (storage, processing, transmission, and sharing) are provided through servers available on the Internet.

Contents

CHAPTER ONE	6
GENERAL INRODACTION	6
1. Introduction	6
1.2 study problem	8
1.3. Study hypothesis	9
1.4 study goal:	9
Chapter tow	10
Literature Review and Previous Studies	10
2.1. Cloud computing	11
2.2. best cloud computing services and developments:.....	13
2.2.1. Microsoft Cloud Services : Microsoft hree Clouds - Azure, Dynamics 365, Microsoft 365	13
2.2.2 IBM Cloud	20
2.2.3. Amazon EC2	22
2.2.4. Citrix Cloud	24
2.2.5 Joyent	26
A. Who owns joyent?	27
Samsung Group Samsung Electronics America Joyent/Parent organizations	27
2.2.6. The Blue Lock	29
2.2.7 . The Verizon Cloud	32
2.2.8. Describe Salesforce.	33
2.2.9. Rackspace	35
2.2.10. What exactly is GCP?	36
2.3. cloud computing and agile development	38
2.4. five Important Types of Agile Methodology (2022).....	40
2.4.1. Kanban	42
2.4.2 Scrum	55
2.4.3. Crystal methodology	63
2.4.4. Extreme Programming (XP)	64
2.4.5. Dynamic Systems Development Method (DSDM)	66
3.1. Cloud migration	83
3.2. Migrate large databases:	84

3.3. migration from on-premises to the cloud work	85
3.4. What is her accreditation The migration strategy to the cloud that organizations must	86
3.5. Which cloud deployment style should companies choose	86
3.6. The main challenges of migrating to the cloud	87
3.7. Now we have to choose the candidate tool to use to build the local cloud	88
3.7.1. Next Cloud	88
3.7.1.1. Features of next cloud	89
3.7.1.2. Advantages and disadvantages	90
3.7.2. own Cloud	90
Chapter four	94
Materials and method	94
4.1. using Agile method	94
4.2. Agile-Project-Plan.....	95
4.3. Agile-Sprint-Backlog-Burndown-Chart.....	96
4.4. Story points	96
4.4. Agile-Release-Plan.....	97
4.5. A strategic overview of the product's medium- and long-term orientation	98
4.6. Product backlog helps the product owner to follow the work of all the features that stakeholders want the product to include.	99
4.7. A user story explains a feature from the viewpoint of the end user	100
4.8. Instead of a static test plan that usually occurs at a certain time	101
4.9. Every project manager aims to produce a brief and straightforward project document, but many take months to prepare one that may contain thousands of words.....	102

CHAPTER ONE

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1. Introduction

Many institutions and companies, especially in the Middle East, suffer from multiple problems with their computer systems. As most of these problems are from The difficulty of providing the appropriate infrastructure and hardware for these programs and the necessary and continuous updates , in addition to limited resources, which is one of the most important points, as The resources available in the local server, whatever their size (the number of processing units and their speed, the number and size of storage devices, etc.), in the end, there are resources, and each resource is characterized by scarcity. (As the optimal goal is to deal with this type of resource, i.e. use it to achieve goals with lowest possible cost and at the high efficiency) (Khalid , A Aljazaery, Th Salim, & Ali , 2021)

Define Cloud computing is a technology that relies on transferring storage space and data stored from the local server to the so-called cloud, i.e. converting information programs from products to services. Working according to the needs of the work opens, which opens new job opportunities and frees the work, making it according to the factors of time and place .

Information technology companies have realized the requirements of cloud work, especially with the wave of the spread of coronaviruses, as it has provided platforms that benefit the user in this field, including (Langmead & Nellore, 2018)

- **MCS - Microsoft Cloud Services**
- **IBM Cloud**
- **Amazon Elastic Compute Cloud**
- **Cloud Citrix**
- **Joyent Cloud**
- **BlueLock Cloud Services.**
- **Verizon Cloud**
- **SalesForce Cloud**
- **Ruby.RackSpace**
- **Google cloud platform**

Technological progress would innovate at an increasing pace. Companies introduce new products in-house in ever shorter time frames. To achieve To panies must resort to agile methods in developing their products. It is a practice traditionally used to rapidly develop software by its developers. Agile builds its iterative approach by focusing on highly collaborative environments and self-organizing teams [5].

We use the agile development methodology in this study because it presents many ways to assess the project's direction during the life cycle progression. If we want any kind of achievement, it requires regular work, like sprints. The Agile model works in every aspect of the purpose, and the business is revisited frequently throughout its lifecycle as the use of cloud computing allows more flexibility in dealing wi servers that have been known on-premises. During this period. Many organizations choose to provide an operating system disk to a server on a storage matrix and use the boot model. The benefit of deploying operating systems this way was: if a single physical server fails, a new server

can replace it, mapped to the same boot volume, and the same OS instance and applications can be backed up and running in no time (Jain1 & Abhishek, 2011)

1.2 study problem

The dependence on the Management of information technology applications for a long time on the local server makes the framework in external access and powers and the work space limited to a specific place and a specific number of people and It requires a series of actions to be taken with any change.

With the expansion and development of the work environment of organizations significantly great challenges have been created for leading ration towards open leading developments I caused which emerged quickly after the Corona era, represented in the need to provide greater material resources and the possibility of multiple access, which generated an increase in cost and time needed for development.

The recent developments in the field of information technology have obligated institutions to make their data available through the cloud, and this is what we will study and implement on the local server, as it ensures the continuity of work and the non-interruption of the service provided through this server, knowing that this work needs a lot of measures that must be taken to ensure Speed, accuracy, no data interference and, no data loss, as well as controlling and protecting authorized access to this data, meaning increased reliability to ensure quality. The agile model was chosen because the combination of rapid Development and cloud computing are a good feature to efficiently meet the needs of users (Ambreen, Ayesha, & ,Muhammad, 2013)

1.3. Study hypothesis

Data access is the primary key to business performance through analysis and processing, and for the effectiveness of this, we will activate an extensive and multi-access cloud data service. We will implement this through an agile model to ensure rapid progress and work conforming to the required specifications

1.4 study goal:

Increasing the effectiveness and efficiency of accessing data on the local server through the use of tools provided by cloud service management companies, which are equivalent in their work and procedures to what is in the local servers, for example (owncloud - Azure Active Directory). Relying on cloud data provides greater capabilities than it provides Traditional local servers, cloud servers created great capabilities to provide the requirements necessary to manage information technology applications and allowed mult I access outside the local network and reduced the costs of physical units, especially after the Corona era, which required employees to carry out their work outside institutions and ensure Accuracy, speed and high implementation of requirements through the use of the agile model. (Sharda & Delen, 2020)

Cloud computing represents a model for convenient and permanent access at any time to the network by sharing a large set of resources of this service that can be deployed and provided with less interaction with the service provider

Chapter tow
Literature Review and Previous Studies

2.1. Cloud computing

The (NIST) " National Institute of standards and technology defines the cloud" ...It is a relatively new business model in the world of computing, based on the demand for a common set of resources (storage / networks / servers- - applications, and services) that can be provided and accessed quickly with minimal effort. Administrative or interaction with the service provider". Therefore, the addition of cloud services to the data, provides quick access to them through the services provided by the cloud, as well as fast processing and large-scale data storage. (Mahmood & Saeed)

A) Where the form includes

"(IaaS) Infrastructure as a Service"

"Platform as a Server (PaaS)"

"Software as a Service (SaaS) "

Although there are many challenges, the use of integrated cloud tools and systems has been proven to reduce cost and help organizations in all directions allowing developers to focus more on building software with less resistance. It supports IaaS, PaaS, and SaaS AGSD cloud services.

- IaaS**

Consumers have direct access to the infrastructure and virtual servers within the network hosted by the cloud service provider. software development through virtualization supports by IaaS allowing servers to be provided on-demand for the project. This allows the project team to work in parallel as in the agile model, reducing the Conflicting parallel workflows on resources

- **PaaS**

software development through virtualization,

Provides cloud users with the ability to use other frameworks and programs in pre-configured instances, which are provided and hosted by the Content Service Platforms. Standard examples of virtualized services with installed and preconfigured software aid in the systems development life cycle of designed software, with the rapid availability of new clean instances Tests include PaaS Cloud Foundry-Windows Azure Google App Engine-Heroku and Microsoft

- **SaaS**

the Users are system administrators end within organizations, as well as individual users who use the Software directly from content service platforms. the Users can access SaaS services via a thin client. Examples of SaaS include Google Apps, Microsoft 365, and Salesforce. SaaS supports development in many ways (Haig-Smith & Tanner, 2016)

B. Why is t

In terms of security, the cloud environment is more flexible with several layers of security compared to more traditional on-premises servers. This is effective as long as a set of conditions are met, which will be discussed below:

A cloud server is very secure if the company is highly reliable or advanced encryption and security software is used where these companies need to take the initiative to activate the security controls provided by the companies providing cloud computing services and also must ensure that these companies have the relevant policies in place and maintain It has up-to-date hardware to ensure data security

Cloud data storage, in addition to surpassing traditional systems in terms of security, is a highly scalable model. The scalability scheme for cloud servers outperforms any other infrastructure we've seen in the past. For these and many other reasons, it is recommended that companies rely on this type of server to host their information and exploit data through cloud monitoring, provided that a reliable provider has experience with these services.

2.2. best cloud computing services and developments:

2.2.1. Microsoft Cloud Services : Microsoft three Clouds - Azure, Dynamics 365, Microsoft 365

A. MICROSOFT AZURE

Azure was announced in February 2010 by Microsoft, which is a fast and flexible public cloud computing platform. In addition, its pricing and many capabilities make it the best public cloud offering in the market, as this service provides a range of standard cloud computing services such as "(storage, applications, software, and infrastructure too)", in employing services based on

exploiting Microsoft's proprietary technologies such as Active Directory and SQL Server Microsoft Azure is unique

The public cloud computing platform provides many different cloud services such as infrastructure as a service (Laas), platform as a service (paas), software as a service (SaaS) that can be used for services such as storage , networking , analytics, , and much more.

The most important features that distinguish Microsoft Azure from other cloud platforms:

- 1. Reliable: have technical support at any time. Reliability 99.95 %**
- 2. The data can be accessed from anywhere in the world and simultaneously.**
- 3. it is more economical because only what you use is paid.**
- 4. Flexible use of resources will be according to the needs of the company, change it and according to its growth**
- 5. Unlocked: supports most operating systems or almost any language, tool or framework.**

What makes Azure essential and ideal for companies is flexibility, scalability, and security, especially for companies that want to work towards IoT solutions. Any of the devices can be easily connected to the cloud using the available tools that enable you to integrate your infrastructure and start collecting new data for your business.

It can also monitor and manage billions of devices and gain information and insights that help make better business decisions and improve customer experiences . Inside the IoT hub powered by Azure ‘ (Wang & Durowoju, 2011)

(Azure website, <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/>)

Figure (1) What services did AZURE provide at the time of writing this research?

B. Dynamics 365

The combination of ERP, CRM software, and reporting functions is considered in the Pi power. It is two separate systems known as AX Dynamics and CRM Dynamics that were combined in 2016 into one system

(The power Pi report is a multi-perspective presentation of the data model, with visualizations representing different results and insights from this data model. The report can contain a single visualization or pages filled with visuals. Depending on your role, you can read and explore reports, or you can create them for others (Microsoft))

1- Data Analytics

Dynamics 365 reads your digit read cords i.e. sales and website visitors to see how much your vehicles have been used. Then you find the perfect patterns. Whatever you order, this service will bring those numbers together into clear reports, including charts, percentages, and helpful insights.

These patterns make it easier for you to learn how a particular business or department is doing, because they allow you to take effective action. For example, you can develop services that customers love, tackle a problem before it occurs, or reward and support employees with more helpful solutions.

2- What's new in 2022

Dynamics 365 Edition 2022 and Industry Cloud, a host of new innovations give you the power to transform your business. This release includes many, if not hundreds, of new features across Dynamics 365 apps, including Sales, Customer Services, Marketing, Field Services, Commerce, Fraud Protection, Business Center, Connected Spaces, Directories, and Remote Assist Customer

Insights Customer Voice Microsoft Cloud for Sustaining Healthcare, Financial Services, and Nonprofits (dynamics-microsoft)

- **marketing**

Dynamics 365 Marketing leverages data and artificial intelligence to improve the building and delivery of marketing content. That makes every interaction count, by responding quickly and in a timely manner to new events based on data values and variables in any Dynamics 365 app, taking action in more seamless ways, using code-free conditional text to easily customize content, and taking instant action on SMS replies from During a personalized experience based on responses with custom keywords.

- **sales**

Dynamics 365 Sales focuses on enabling the sales professional to harness the power of data and artificial intelligence to predict and compare annual forecasts and measure performance with these results. Collaboration vendors can use teams from within Dynamics 365 to accelerate their product line, while managers can evaluate team performance and suggest training to increase customer satisfaction. The goal is to help the seller complete a number of transactions quickly with maximum productivity.

- **Services**

Dynamics 365 customer service focuses on settings that benefit administrators and during the new customer service management center will change, update and change the way the agent's inbox is displayed . To optimize agent productivity improvements to Microsoft Teams include Dynamics 365 data

integration with AI-suggested contacts and AI-generated conversation summaries for agents. (release wave 1 plan)

- **365 Field Service**

Dynamics provides schedule board usability and innovation improvements that allow for faster and easier use, and improve dispatcher productivity. The Field Service mobile app has features and improvements that improve technician productivity and is supported on Windows.

Figure (2) What's new in 2022

C. THE Microsoft 365

is a productivity cloud designed to help achieve and manage business goals. It combines best-in-class productivity apps like Word, Excel, and PowerPoint, With powerful cloud services, advanced security and Device Management in one connected experience.

Use the professional calendar and email to communicate to customers and co-workers wherever you are. File storage, access and sharing is available from anywhere with 1 TB of storage per patron . Teamwork is always required with group chats, online meetings, and calls in Microsoft Teams . This teamwork helps protect your data, employees and beneficiaries ' information through advanced security and device management.. (HUSAINI)

Figuar (3) THE Microsoft 365 IN 2022

2.2.2 IBM Cloud

IBM is redefining what the cloud really means. Where it provides more than (IaaS) as part of the scope of its services within the IBM Cloud, It is easy to determine the final cost during communication with the company. The services include a group of typical public clouds with a group of local services bearing the IBM brand.

An example of this is setting up a regular server as is the procedure with a traditional hosting company, this is available inside IBM Cloud. Or it could also provide fully virtualized infrastructure and cloud-style software, or even developer services or access to the giant IBM Watson and Watson Assistant. Despite these advantages and the excellent rating that the beneficiary receives, he does not outperform his competitor Amazon Web Services (AWS) in the EIAs Solutions Review Report (Rash, 2018)

- **Positives**

Strong performance.

Supports 40 GB networks.

Provides access to a lot of data centers.

- **Negatives**

The setup is not as intuitive for beginners as other services like Rackspace.

IBM Cloud provides Data Center Cloud Services as well as many of the solutions you need in IBM Services to take advantage of applications While IBM Services may be a necessity for some things, the fact that full services are

available is a big plus. Here you will find options not available in any other service. IBM Cloud Catalog integration means a wide range of options and can provide many very granular options regarding (processors, memory, VMs, network type, storage type, and - rather than just providing a small, medium or large size of the virtual machine (VM) You can integrate regular servers into your own cloud, even though the hardware is not on your site but you have full control of it because you are a distributor of these servers entirely from IBM,

IBM Cloud allows the use of an Enterprise Infrastructure Management System (IMS) to control it. With that said, your primary interface is IBM Cloud Catalog for most activities.

Recording, billing, alerting, saving and canceling savings is done through Cloud Catalog. IBM Cloud also includes an IMS Application Programming Interface (API) that exposes all the capabilities of the cloud using REST. In short, if your IT team includes good programmers, it is relatively easy to integrate EMS into web-based infrastructure management tools. (Rash, 2018)

Figuar (4) IBM cloud in 2022

2.2.3. Amazon EC2

short for Amazon Elastic Compute Cloud, is an Amazon web service that provides flexible and scalable computing power in the cloud and is designed to make cloud computing at scale easier for developers. (Amazon Cloud)

A. Amazon EC2 Features

- **Instances are virtual computing environments**
- **Ready - made templates for statuses known as "Amazon machine images" that pack the bits you need for the server as well as additional software and your operating system**
- **The difference of components for CPU, storage, memory and network capacity in your instances, known as instance types**
- **Using key pairs secure the login information for your instances where AWS stores the public key , and the private key can be stored in a safe place , And store temporary data that is deleted when an instance is stopped, hibernated, or terminated, also known as instance volumes**
- **Fixed data volumes using Amazon Elastic block store which are known as volumes**
- **Multiple locations for your resources such as Amazon EBS volumes and instances known as zones and Availability Zones**
- **enables you to specify by firewall the source protocols, ports, and IP ranges through which your instances can be accessed using security groups**
- **Static IPv4 addresses for dynamic cloud computing, known as Elastic IP Addresses**
- **Metadata known as tags that you can create and customize for your Amazon EC2 resources**

- **Virtual networks that you can create that are logically isolated from the rest of the Amazon Web Services cloud, You can optionally connect to your own network known as Virtual Private Cloud.**

A high-capacity computing environment and a user interface that allows the user to have full control over computing resources in the Amazon computing environment.

EC2 is a very economical service that allows you to pay only for the capacity you use. Amazon EC2 provides developers with tools to build powerful applications that are as fail-free as possible and enable them to avoid common mistakes that often occur. (Amazon Cloud)

B. What features does Amazon EC2 have?

Computing flexibility: EC2 enables you to increase or decrease capacity or storage capacity according to your needs in just a few minutes and apply it to one, 100, or even a thousand servers simultaneously.

Full control and control: You have full control over the virtual servers and you can interact with them as you would any machine where you can stop the server while keeping the data in the boot partition and later you can restart the server.

Flexible cloud hosting: You can choose from several types of servers, instances, operating systems and software packages. Allows you to choose to configure: Memory, CPU, instance server storage and boot partition appropriate to your choice of operating system and applications. (Amazon Cloud)

Figuar (5) AWS services in 2022

2.2.4. Citrix Cloud

March 28, 2022 Citrix Cloud is a platform that hosts and administers Citrix cloud services. It connects to your resources through connectors on any cloud or infrastructure you choose (on-premises, public cloud, private cloud, or hybrid cloud). It allows you to create, manage, and deploy workspaces with apps and data to your end-users from a single console

it is a cloud-based system for managing and deploying Citrix products, desktops and applications to end users, using any type of cloud whether private, public, hybrid or on-premise. The product supports cloud-based versions of every major Citrix product. Can be accessed together independently or as an integrated workspace (berger)

A. Features

For the Citrix products XenApp, XenDesktop, XenMobile, ShareFile, and NetScaler, Citrix Cloud allows cloud services.

Additionally, Citrix has created a number of essential cloud services, such as the Safe Browser service.

The Citrix Cloud Connector enables synchronization of Citrix Cloud with any data center, device, and cloud. Citrix has stated that Microsoft Azure is their primary cloud partner as of May 2016. Although Citrix platforms are housed in Citrix Cloud, other resources and applications could gain from the cloud and other infrastructures.

The IT department of the business is still allowed to pick from a personalized list of data centers and cloud service providers. Citrix is always improving Citrix Cloud so that users will automatically find that they are running the latest version (wikipedia)

B. What's new

The objective of Citrix is to offer Citrix DaaS customers new features and product updates as soon as they become available. There is no reason to put off updates because new releases offer more value. Be aware that updates for Citrix DaaS are provided roughly every three weeks.

The user may easily understand and follow this process. Initial upgrades are only made to Citrix on-premises sites, and customer environments receive them gradually after that. Waves of incremental upgrades help enhance availability and ensure product quality. (Citrix Product Documentation, 2022)

Figure (6) CITRIX in 2022

2.2.5 Joyent

a high-performance cloud infrastructure provider offering the only available method for running mobile and web applications instantly.

Businesses require a scalable, tested, and built-in cloud infrastructure that works immediately. The expectations of an immediate worldwide expansion cannot be met by traditional cloud infrastructure. The economics of both public and private cloud computing are significantly altered by Joyent's cloud infrastructure, which offers a multiplier effect of up to 50% lower cost and twice the performance in this instance. Businesses can cease paying for peak times and price increases with Joyent and only meet basic demand. By utilizing a single public or private cloud infrastructure, or both, they can also achieve a new degree of operational skill and control. (Sharma)

Joyent is the only cloud infrastructure that delivers extraordinary performance from a virtual machine, enabling applications to run faster and more reliably than a traditional public or private cloud infrastructure.

Complete visibility, security, and control over applications can be achieved through the simplified Joyent stack and unique cloud analytics enable businesses to

Real-time latency analysis and the only self-service performance tools available in the industry help you anticipate and prevent issues before they arise. Additionally, it provides specialized performance and debugging capabilities for Node.js applications as a Node.js agent. Companies can revolutionize how they manage and scale cloud apps thanks to these capabilities. Technologically astute leaders at some of the most demanding businesses in the world have tapped into the power of Joyent's cloud architecture to enjoy the visibility, security, and control of dedicated servers in the cloud. (wikipedia)

A. Who owns joyent?

Samsung Group

Samsung Electronics America

Joyent/Parent organizations

B. What kind of support do you get with Joyent?

Joyent engineers provide 360 degree support for modern application architectures, including microservices, apis, development frameworks and container-native devops tooling. Discover Node.js Support. (joyent-cloud)

C. What do you like best?

Its cross-platform ability to go from Linux to windows and even to Mac allows users to utilize the program with any computer, which is enormous when coming to user practicality. I think another viable and useful ability will be the ability to improve effeciency, which generally is one of the aspects that take forever to improve, but with this program and application it completely reduces the time of change.Review collected by and hosted on G2.com.

D. What do you dislike?

Some might say there is a slight issue with being too simple, and there are at times, having to navigate and find the right action versus what the easiest one is. Another issue I can see being a troublesome aspect is that even though things are cross-platform, doesnt necessearily mean it will sync on command. Be sure to check what is being moved to a cloud and what is not.Review collected by and hosted on G2.com.

E. Recommendations to others considering the product:

Consider using it even when you have people using a different OS; the ability to sync across all platforms makes life a lot easier, especially with the entire work-from-home schedule that is going around. Make sure you also see what employees find satisfying about the program as well. Everyone being on board especially with a user friendly program is crucial.Review collected by and hosted on G2.com.

F. What problems is the product solving and how is that benefiting you?

Cost reduction has always been the issue with companies ranging from where you can cut dollars and still be effective. With this application and its various uses, it allows you to be multi-faceted and get what you need to be done, done. Along with cost you always want to have new systems be simple to use and with older folks in the work force and some not being computer savvy, you want to implement software that makes it reliable for them but also for everyone to use.

Figure (7) joyent cloud in 2022

2.2.6. The Blue Lock

company specializing in cloud computing and disaster recovery expertise for the Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) . BlueLock provides its clients with the personnel, knowledge, and IT infrastructure they need. in 70 certified data center.

The business offers Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), which enables customers to sign up on a monthly basis for the exact amount of compute, storage, and

bandwidth they need right now with the possibility of future "on-demand" growth. Their distinct IT environments are perfect for Web-based software (also known as SaaS or Web 2.0) and systems that need high availability and the flexibility to dynamically grow and contract for production or disaster recovery.. BlueLock, Inc. Collina Ventures is privately owned and headquartered in Indianapolis, Indiana. (bluelock)

A. Why Choose Bluelock for VMware Cloud Hosting?

- Bluelock offers 7+ years of enterprise cloud hosting experience in industries like finance, healthcare, technology & more.**
- Bluelock is a VMware vCloud Datacenter certified provider and a VMware-approved cloud credit service provider.**
- Our solution architects work with customers to design a customized cloud environment featuring production-grade hosting, utility hosting and Recovery-as-a-Service (cloud-based DR).**
- The Bluelock Portfolio™ portal enables customers to optimize cloud infrastructure with full visibility to detailed usage data, resources available and current and projected cloud costs.**
- Bluelock Recovery-as-s-Service offers peace of mind for your most important applications, with two free tests per year.**
- Customers can choose self-service, partial or fully managed cloud services along with superior support options and advisory services.**
- Private MPLS, point-to-point or WAN network connectivity to our data centers for highest reliability and best performance.**
- Customized firewall solutions offer enterprise-level security.**
- Create & manage hybrid clouds with vCloud Connector and vCloud Director to securely link private clouds to public clouds.**

Bluelock Technology Compatibility Specifications Bluelock is committed to providing your organization with the latest and greatest major technology releases to power your solution. However, because we are also deeply committed to the stability of both your environment and ours, we take our time upgrading to ensure success for both your team and ours. The success and reliability of your Bluelock solution relies on the compatibility of your VMware versions and Bluelock's solutions. In order to ensure that success, mutual coordination is key before any technology and software upgrades occur.

Disaster Recovery The following DRaaS technology providers are a sample of the those supported today by Bluelock: - Zerto - Double-Take - Veeam - Commvault - We also support client-chosen replication tools as part of tailored-service engagements. When replicating from your own site, to Bluelock's cloud, to ensure successful recovery,

Figure (8) bluelock cloud

2.2.7 . The Verizon Cloud

You can store photos, videos, documents and other data using the application that is available via Android or iOS phones, tablets, Windows and Mac computers.

It is considered a service that provides secure cloud storage for wireless backup and also synchronizes content between your phone, tablet, computer and other devices. (Snider, 2021)

A. What is Verizon Cloud In 2022?

Verizon Cloud is one of the many services that Verizon offers customers that allows you to securely store your content, including pictures, contacts documents, and videos. You can sync and backup all of your data wirelessly on all of your devices including tablets, computers, phones, and other similar devices. With Verizon Cloud, you can view content anytime you want privately. (verizon-cloud)

Figure (9) Verizon Cloud In 2022

2.2.8. Describe Salesforce.

is a well-known American provider of CRM services that uses cloud-based technologies. For support, marketing, and sales teams everywhere in the world, Salesforce is a well-liked CRM application. Salesforce enables companies to use cloud computing to improve communication with partners, clients, and potential clients. These businesses may track customer behavior, promote to clients, and provide many more services by using Salesforce CRM.

The CRM platform aids in delving deeply into all of your metrics and data; the user can also build up a control panel that visually represents his data. Automation can also be used to obtain individualized awareness. Another significant advantage is that a CRM system can enhance customer service's capacity to assist clients or reach out to the sales force. (By Simplilearn, 2022)

A. building Salesforce

- 1. Multi-tenant: Salesforce uses a single database schema to hold all of the data. where it is feasible to have one software server instance with many tenants. In terms of architecture, multi-tenancy refers to the use of a single shared application service by numerous clients. It is therefore economical. On the other hand, a single customer is entirely responsible for the development and maintenance costs in a single tenancy. Therefore, it is a typical multi-tenant architecture.**
- 2. Metadata: A development paradigm used by Salesforce is built on metadata. It enables programmers to concentrate solely on creating the application. Scaling and customisation are simple with our metadata-driven platform.**

3. **API:** Salesforce has an effective source API available. This aids in the creation and customization of the mobile Salesforce1 app. Every element of Salesforce's design was carefully thought out and put into place. **Services from Salesforce**

B. Services offered by Salesforce:

- **“SAAS (Software as a Service)”:** Here you can directly access and benefit from the built-in software.
- **PAAS (Platform as a Service):** PAAS provides you with a framework and platform for creating your own websites and applications.
- **IAAS (Infrastructure as a Service):** IAAS plays a vital role in the development of Salesforce, although it is not widely used. (By Simplilearn, 2022)

Figure (10) Describe Salesforce

2.2.9. Rackspace

It is a cloud computing business whose aim is to make the deployment of both private and public clouds easier to manage.

The business, which offers proficiency across cloud platforms like Amazon Web Services, Microsoft Cloud/Azure, and OpenStack, is regarded as the largest managed cloud provider.

Rackspace provides services including fervent OS and Microsoft Azure support. The advantages of public cloud deployments are intended to be maximized by these services.

It is a collection of auxiliary computing-based cloud computing services and products from the American business Rackspace. Offers include virtual private servers, load balancers, databases, backup, and monitoring along with cloud storage ("cloud files"). Cloud by Rackspace (rackspace)

The 2022 ISG Provider Lens™ Next-Gen Private / Hybrid Cloud - Data Center Services & Solutions Report ranks managed hosting and services administered by the public sector in the United States, according to Rackspace Technology, a pioneer in end-to-end technology solutions and various clouds.

The lack of IT skills is one of the major IT challenges globally, according to research from Rackspace Technology. To provide customers with fully managed public and private cloud services, including end-to-end cloud services and data transformation, Rackspace sends in its army of qualified and experienced technicians. "ISG's acknowledgement of our leadership in this crucial

The advantages, trade-offs in the market, and distinctive selling factors of the top service providers in each market.

The surge in distant business performance during the COVID-19 pandemic is merely the most well-known trend affecting IT operations, according to the 2022 ISG Provider Lens™ Next-Gen Private/Hybrid Cloud report.

The public sector's IT requirements are evolving as a result of cyber security concerns, an increase in the need for sophisticated computing, employee shortages, server equipment reaching the end of its useful life or depreciating, and staff shortages. The solution for many organizations is to move more IT jobs to cloud services. (Rackspace)

Figure (11) Rackspace technology in 2022

2.2.10. GCP?

Like its rivals Microsoft Azure and Amazon Web Services, GCP is a public cloud resource. Customers can use computer resources housed in Google Centers all over the world for free or on a pay-per-use basis by using GCP and other cloud vendors.

GCP provides a wide range of computing services for tasks including monitoring GCP costs, managing data, and displaying web pages and videos, in addition to providing tools for machine learning and artificial intelligence.

Google Cloud vs. Google Cloud Platform

A variety of online services from Google Cloud are available to assist businesses in going digital. Web-based applications are hosted on a public cloud architecture by Google Cloud Platform. (Karlos Knox, 2021)

Other services offered by Google Cloud include some of the following:

- Google Workspace, also referred to as Google Apps and G Suite. Gmail, collaborative tools, and enterprise identity management are available.**
- Chrome OS and Android in enterprise editions. There are ways to communicate with web-based apps using mobile devices and mobile operating systems.**
- Application programming interfaces (APIs), i.e., services for businesses and organizations that use machine learning and mapping. These establish links between several programs.**

The backbone of many applications forms Google's GCP cloud architecture is like Google in the workplace, these applications are not what we are talking about when we talk about GCP. For this position (Karlos Knox, 2021)

A. What's New With Google Cloud for 2022

Google Cloud Platform's products and solutions continue to grow and get better into the new year. With what's new with Google Cloud for 2022,

Figure (12) Google Cloud in 2022

2.3. cloud computing and agile development

Agile development approaches and cloud computing work very well together. While agile approaches offer flexibility and high credibility for the user to collaborate frequently in the discovery of requirements, cloud computing immediately satisfies customer requirements. The goal of agile software development is to divide (project needs) into manageable chunks. This process makes sure that user input is documented throughout the whole project development process. For the purpose of upholding high quality standards and virtually eliminating bottlenecks, segment design, development, and testing can be done independently. Thus, each component's development phase is reduced to a single "iteration" step. Agile software also has a lot of potential for

emphasizing the formation of cooperative relationships between application developers and end users . (Abhishek & Reena , 2011)

Figure (13) cloud computing

Because the end user can easily understand and follow this development process, they may provide input at any time and adjustments can be made as a result.

A highly dynamic and collaborative environment is provided by the usage of cloud computing and Agile development. Developers can publish a feature as a cloud service as soon as it is complete, allowing users to review it right away and offer insightful comments. Thus, a detailed

Eliminating the feedback cycle lowers the possibility of distorted or misinterpreted requirements [4]. As a result, a software development organization's time and effort are greatly reduced, and end users are more satisfied. (Abhishek & Reena , 2011)

Figure (14) agile with cloud computing

2.4. Eight Important Types of Agile Methodology (2022)

Below we list the top 5 types of Agile methodology

In order to keep pace with the rapid changes that have grown in the technological model, agile technology was born, which is defined as a clear shift in project management as opposed to the traditional waterfall model.

The development of agile software development methodologies appeared in 2001, and was based on the most venerated agile manifesto which outlined core principles and practices. Since before we understand the definition of agile methodologies, it is best to know what agile is.

Agile is defined as a set of techniques followed by a project management team or a business plan by dividing it into different phases in sync with continuous cooperation with clients. That is, there is continuous monitoring at every stage of the project's software development. The advantages of agile methodology are that both development and testing procedures are parallel and concurrent, unlike the traditional waterfall methodology (Sarangam, 8 Important Types Of Agile Methodology (2022), 2021)

- 1. "Kanban**
- 2. Scrum**
- 3. Extreme Programming (XP)**
- 4. Crystal**
- 5. Dynamic Systems Development Method (DSDM)**
- 6. Feature Driven Development (FDD)**
- 7. Lean Software Development**
- 8. Scaled Agile Framework (SAFe)**

One of the simplest and most difficult methods to turn a variety of ideas or needs into useful software solutions is through the use of the agile methodology. The agile method is an iterative and incremental strategy for creating programs that make use of ongoing planning, comprehension, promotion, development, and teamwork. Teams work on separate models where the agile process is fractured, Thus encouraging flexibility in changes.

Agile emerges with consumers who identify or interfere with the end uses of the end product and the kinds of problems the final product is seeking to address. Agile is guided by the principles of value delivery and cooperation with

stakeholders. The requirements of the project development team and the expectations of the client are defined and made clearer through this activity. As soon as a project is launched, the team starts planning and develops a full process through preparation, execution, and assessment. The project's middle phase will see problems fixed because the development process is iterative. The final deliverable product can better meet the customer's needs thanks to this approach. Every framework or behavior that deals with these principles is called Agile. Although different types of Agile methodologies can be implemented by a team, the benefits of an agile methodology can only be fully understood in collaboration with all stakeholders.

Below the list of Agile methodologies includes well-known types of agile that the user can choose from: (Sarangam, Important Types Of Agile Methodology (2022), 2022)

2.4.1. Kanban

Kanban is defined as a visual approach to managing a business as it goes through a process. Kanban shows both the workflow and the actual work being done as part of that process using a visual system

Kanban identifies and corrects potential bottlenecks in the work process so that the work flows correctly and at a high productivity rate.

Figure (15) What is Kanban?

A. Kanban Board?

First of all, you should know what we mean by kanban boards and cards.

Keep in mind that the board is divided into vertical lanes, with each lane representing a stage in your process. The far left lane always contains work steps or items that have not yet started, while the far right lane always contains work steps or items that have been completed.

The action begins in Kanban on the left side of the board and progresses towards the right:

Note that work items that have not yet started are placed in the backlog. Those that are created and not completed move to a column in progress and those that are completed move to a separate completed column.

Product Backlog ("To Do") - breaks down the board so that items enter the process from the far left. Accumulate items that have not yet started.

The work in progress is located in the painting section where work began. It is the pillar on which the work must actively move towards completion.

Completed (Done) - This is the section of the board where the completed work goes. Work must go from Completed on the far right to In Progress when new work is started.

Kanban boards can also show you information about your actions beyond just visualizing the stages.

Figure (16) Kanban Board

B. Kanban cards?

In kanban, business items are represented by cards, where these sticky notes on the board can be compared. Many organizations are starting with a physical Kanban board that reflects their current operation. Where each card or sticky note represents one job item.

Figure (16) of boards and kanban cards is very basic

The above figure of boards and kanban cards is very basic, and shows how to use these tools. You can visualize almost any action, at any level of the organization, by moving the cards from left to right through specific stages in the process and providing information on the cards.

Kanban is very flexible, as some of the basic kanban principles and techniques will help reach the goals

C. work visualization

Workflow can be monitored through the kanban system by drawing a visual model of the job and your business processes. Increased communication and collaboration results by making work visible and visible indicators of obstructions, bottlenecks, and queues. It helps show where the team should focus their efforts to increase flow.

The key stage in adopting and implementing the kanban method is either on a physical board or an electronic kanban board - in the process that is used to deliver a work or service a kanban board can be essential for complexity, depending on the complexity of the process and the work mix, the many types of work items you deal with You must take into account a picture of the actions taken, and you will be able to see the current work you are doing.

D. Limit work-in-process

Speeding up the movement of items through the kanban system is possible by recording the amount of unfinished work in progress. Task-switching problems can be avoided and re-prioritization reduced. The limits of the work in progress allow the team to achieve more meaningful results than ever before in a safer and more sustainable way.

Determining the work in progress WIP is critical to the success of Kanban, the "Pull" system.

The idea is that you encourage your team to finish existing tasks before starting new work by limiting work in progress. Uncompleted tasks should be finished

and marked as completed. It creates system capacity, and allows new work to be drawn in. According to Don Reinertsen, initial work in progress while your team starts using Kanban may begin without Work In Progress and Watch limits. Determine the work in progress constraints for each stage of the workflow with half of the average work in progress after sufficient data is obtained.

Typically, many teams are doing 1.5 times the number of people working in progress at a given stage. Restricting WIP and limiting each WIP column to the Team Members panel helps finish what they're doing before moving on to new things and sending the customer a message that there is limited capacity. Note that cycle time determines the average time taken to complete a task.

E. Focus on Flow / Flow Management

The kanban system for your business can be improved by applying work constraints in the process and team-led regulations, as described in these two organizations: The following principles can be used to improve your kanban system for your business:

- **Workflow improvements**
 - **For flow analysis and data collection.**
 - **Be proactive in identifying potential problems by monitoring these indicators.**
- If the course of action is continuous it will be beneficial to deliver faster and more reliable, it will benefit the customers, the team and the organization. The advantage of Kanban that saves money and time is the ability to identify areas for continuous improvement.

This system allows the work flow to be tracked by displaying the different stages of workflow and the status of each stage. Depending on how your process is defined and WIP limits are implemented, it will be obvious either a smooth

flow within WIP or a backlog where something gets delayed and starts to clog capacity. Note that this affects how the work moves from start to finish in the workflow (it can be said as a value flow). Kanban helps your team modify and analyze the system for tasks to move more quickly through the process

Figure (17) What is Kanban Used For?

adoption of the original manufacturing Kanban to knowledge-based work started with a jump right into software development and though other industries have begun to follow the trend fairly quickly today Kanban is still very popular and well-suited for software development processes.

Kanban allows the creation of a continuous workflow one with as little waiting time between process stages as possible where incoming items are dealt with in a steady and timely manner also because the process is visibly accessible recorded and easy to alter customer change requests can be addressed very quickly what we're looking at is a simple Kanban tool board illustrating a software development process with just two card colors one for regular and one for urgent tasks

this where users stories general preconditions and loose ideas get placed once these make it further into being accepted for development their cards are moved to requirement analysis or get archived as not acted upon analysis is aware final preparations and discussion with stakeholders take place from here items reach the development stage modules and features are queued up and waiting and assigned to specific team members as developers become available they pick tasks from waiting and place them in working on after this it's time to test the code Quality Assurance column is split into two stages in the same way that requirements are waiting and doing here however tasks don't receive team member assignments instead any available tester picks up the topmost card and starts working on it if tests prove the items to work correctly cards can be moved further right into verified

but if the work presents bugs cards are reversed to development start their journey once more oftentimes this process loop repeats before modules are successfully verified once checked and confirmed the software modules are ready to be deployed after that all that's left to do with the cards is to move them to done and later archived for the record thanks to use of swim lanes our team is able to progress a number of different projects without becoming confused and losing track of their tasks also in the event of any tie ups in one project the team can move focus to items in the other ones making good use of their time workflow visualization along with use of work-in-progress limits and measuring the average lead time of item completion makeup condoms three core principles following these teams become better equipped to meet their goals and wrap their heads around what needs doing next the whip limit is applied to these columns and is set to one task per person with this the team stands a good chance of ensuring high quality performance with as few Corrections needed as possible this board is using a number of extra features

namely the calendar widget highlighting due dates interactive checklists which let the team see and tick off to-do lists directly from the board view checklist templates that allow making ready-made to-do lists to be included in any tasks with one click task summary showing chosen information on the card fronts thanks to following the work items progress online the team is able to collaborate with developers from around the world and maintain close-knit communication between all employees in one easy-to-use application the amount of time and discussion saved by having everything in one place is great but increased efficiency clear overview of progress and better process predictability are the top benefits of using Kanban tool

F. Five workplace trends of 2022 that Kanban can help with

In today's rapidly advancing world, the environment for the growth and development of a business can change suddenly and dramatically. That's why it's so important to keep your finger on the pulse of the latest trends to be prepared for how they will affect your business. Let's take a look at the 5 latest workplace trends and how Kanban can help you adapt to new realities.

Completely remote companies have become a reality

According to the recent article by Brian Lufkin on the BBC, Yelp, Airbnb, 3M, Spotify and Lyft have recently changed to a completely remote model. Some companies even choose to close their offices completely. As the article states, this was the case for the paid work of the TaskRabbit application that closed all workspaces, including the headquarters in San Francisco. At the same time, other companies, such as Yelp and PayPal, are reducing the number of their physical offices in different cities

Despite the obvious advantages, such as savings on renting workspace, expanding the complex or possible appointments, the entire remote format also

has its drawbacks. While it expands the range of choice of the workforce, it also reduces it for those who want to work full-time remotely, without any option to go to the office even periodically. What we have seen from the pandemic is that although it works, it is not suitable for everyone and not permanently.

To work successfully in a remote or hybrid environment, managers and leaders need to change their way of thinking to view their organization as a network of interconnected services, and all individuals as a single service. The Kanban Method reinforces this vision and can help companies adjust their operations to new business environments.

Figure (18) workplace in kabban

1- Skills

According to an article on Fortune, the post-pandemic world has opened a huge great resignation fund that "shows no signs of slowing down". People give up their jobs in search of higher salaries, better benefits and more satisfying work. The inflation rate also played its role. As a result, a large number of people are switching to a different industry, looking for non-traditional roles, or

opportunities to start their own business. Fewer and fewer of those who left work began to return to their traditional office jobs. Pandemic played its part here too, popularizing remote work and freelance working hours that led to employees looking for more flexibility.

The article says that the number of employees who are thinking about changing jobs is currently about 40% according to recent surveys conducted by Microsoft and McKinsey .

Along with this, the rapidly advancing digitization creates an imbalance in the labor force market: it does not keep pace with the adaptation of the skill set of workers necessary for new emerging jobs. Hence, a lot of companies are struggling to find the people they need. The current volume of staff turnover only exacerbates the situation.

Companies are trying to compete for talent by offering more and more additional incentives to attract or retain valuable employees. And education for employees is one of them.

According to the magazine's data, employers are used to spending about 80% of the professional development budget on higher-paid employees. However, large companies, such as Amazon, Macy's and Starbucks, already offer various educational opportunities for their workers at all levels. This trend will only expand in the near future as more and more employers will offer education as an advantage to attract or retain valuable talent.

It would seem that the Times of the employee's professional development course are over forever. Apparently, in the short term, employees will be looking for ways to add more credentials to their resumes, and companies will be looking for courses that they can offer to their coworkers. Learning and applying the Kanban method is always a win-win. Knowing how to work with Kanban will not only help employees expand their work options, but also the use of the

Kanban method by employees within the company will help improve its efficiency and agility

Figure (19) skill

2- People's culture First

In order to retain high-value employees, companies will also pay more attention to their internal culture. Maintaining a comfortable work climate and avoiding overtime to maintain a healthy work-life balance has become a priority . Moreover, in view of the shortage of suitable personnel in the market, companies prefer to work harder on employee retention and development than on the search for new employees.

Caring for people in the first place has become a necessity from the top to the bottom of companies. Besides, the right culture and leadership can help optimize processes and become more agile as a business.

According to the "4 Day Week Global", 63% of companies found it easier to attract and retain talent within 4 days a week.

Moreover, a Qualtrics survey in 2022 among more than 1,000 American employees showed that 92% are in favor of working four days a week even if it means working longer hours. Therefore, we can see that the wonderful four working days a week can become a reality, just as the 44-hour working week was changed to 40 hours in 1940 under the pressure of a powerful labor movement. In a series of articles by David J Anderson School of Management, you can explore how we can use Kanban concepts to adapt them to the reality of the 4-day work week.

Figure (20) People's culture First

3- More flexibility outside of software development Software

Entrepreneurs see agile as a technology for producing better and faster software products. Certainly, the successful results of agile approaches have been known for a while outside the IT industry. Hence, more and more sectors and companies are trying to apply Agile principles. We see that in 2022 it is

progressing even more, since its main advantages, such as accelerated time to market, transparency, predictable delivery, costs are something they also want to achieve.

You can apply the Kanban Method to any area or business such as financial or legal services, geological sciences, pharmaceutical research, architecture, civil engineering, advertising, market research, technology development, etc., for example, you can explore a successful case study applying the Kanban method with the help of the Kanban Maturity model for BBVA Bank Financial Management. This case study showed the promising results of a 28% reduction in administrative expenses in the bank's internal finance department after their two-year experience with the Kanban Method. (Sarangam, 8 Important Types Of Agile Methodology (2022), 2021)

Figure (21) More flexibility outside of software development Software

2.4.2 Scrum

What the Scrum framework entails

Teams use the Scrum management framework to self-organize and work toward a common objective. In order to deliver projects efficiently, this framework outlines a set of meetings, resources, and roles. It's similar to a sports team getting ready for a major game since Scrum training enables teams to self-manage, draw lessons from past mistakes, and adjust to change. The Scrum framework is used by software teams to develop long-lasting, cost-effective solutions to challenging issues. (digite magazine)

Here are some principles and values that characterize the Scrum framework methodology:

Principles of the Scrum framework for project success

A. Transparency

Teams operate in a setting where everyone is conscious of the difficulties that others could encounter. The multidisciplinary team's regular face-to-face interactions with the project owners eliminate information-based misunderstandings and performance issues.

B. Reflection

The framework includes recurring reflection points to enable team members to assess their performance. Estimates and future plans are made by project managers using the information gained from these review meetings. As a result, tasks can be completed more quickly, inexpensively, and in accordance with the planned timeline.

C. Adaptation

Tasks can be reordered by team members in accordance with shifting customer demands. They have the option to choose which duties to finish first and which to focus on later.

D. Scrum values for project teams: Scrum teams adhere to five core values.

1- Commitment

The members of a scrum team commit to completing the tasks and achieving the deadlines for the goals, and they work continuously to improve their processes to come up with the best solutions.

2- Courage Scrum Teams display courage by posing probing, challenging questions. To come up with the greatest answer, they are having open and sincere discussions.

3- Focus

Team members will work on completing tasks according to the product backlog task list at any given time. They will concentrate on finishing certain activities in a short amount of time.

4- Openness Team members using the Scrum Framework are receptive to fresh perspectives and chances that promote both individual growth and high project standards.

5- Respect

The Scrum Framework process, project managers, and other team members are all respected by the team. Respectful teamwork is fostered by this culture, which also fosters cooperation among teammates.

E. Scrum framework's tools?

Scrum teams employ "Scrum framework tools" known as Scrum Artifacts to manage projects and solve problems. The planning and task information provided by the Scrum framework tools is crucial for stakeholders and team members. Three fundamental devices exist:

1- List of Product Tasks (Product Backlog)

A product to-do list is a dynamic list of features, specifications, upgrades, and repairs that must be finished in order for a project to be successful. It essentially consists of a list of Team tasks that are regularly evaluated and re-prioritized to reflect changes in the market. The product owner keeps the list current, deletes undesirable work items, and may also include new client orders.

2- Sprint task list (Sprint Backlog)

The development team has a list of tasks it has to do during the current "Sprint cycle" called the Sprint to-do list. The team chooses the work items to be finished from the product task list before to the start of each Sprint. Throughout the Sprint cycle, the Sprint to-do list can adapt and modify due to its flexibility.

3- Partial products (Increment)

A partial product is a step toward a vision or objective. After the Sprint cycle is over, it is the last usable product. Teams can use a variety of methods to specify and illustrate their sprint goals. Despite the adaptability of Sprint Goals, the fundamental Sprint Goal, or the outcomes the team has established for the current Sprint cycle, cannot be compromised.

For example, some teams choose to launch a product for their customers at the end of the Sprint cycle, so the Sprint goal is accomplished as soon as the changes

in the program are published. Other teams may be working to complete a set of features that will be launched at the same time. In this case, the Sprint Goal will be completed when the feature is successfully tested.

F. the Scrum events

Scrum teams routinely hold a series of meetings known as Scrum events or Scrum celebrations. The following are some of the Scrum framework events:

1. Sprint course planning (Sprint Planning)

The team is grateful for the work that will be accomplished in the upcoming Sprint session at this time. Members establish attainable, detailed, and measurable goals for the Sprint course. Each Scrum member will have learned how to deliver each of the partial products in the Sprint cycle by the end of the planning meeting.

2. Sprint course

The Scrum team collaborates to deliver incomplete products over the course of a sprint. A Sprint course typically lasts two weeks, though this might change based on the team's and the project's demands. The Sprint cycle will be shorter the more difficult the work is and the more unknown challenges there are.

G. Daily Scrum meeting or standing meeting

Daily Scrum meetings are quick gatherings where team members participate in day-to-day planning. Along with reporting on work completed, they discuss any difficulties encountered in accomplishing Sprint Goals. Because it seeks to make the meeting brief and useful at the same time, as when everyone is standing, it is known as a "standing meeting."

1. Sprint Review

The team meets informally at the conclusion of the Sprint course to assess the work completed and to present it to stakeholders. Depending on the outcomes of the current Sprint course, the product owner may also change the product task list..

2. Review of previous Sprint results

The team comes together to document and discuss achievements and failures during the Sprint course. The ideas put forward are used to improve the performance of future Sprint courses.

The 6 Best Scrum Project Management Tools

let's take a look at some of these scrum tools in detail.

1. Jira

- Pricing: Free; cheapest plan costs \$7.50 per month**
- Website: atlassian.com/software/jira**

Pros:

Excellent free version

Cheap paid plans

Made for software companies

Great kanban & scrum boards

Cons:

Not very useful for hybrid teams

Too much jargon

Discount needs more than 100 users

If you're even slightly at home with project management, you're probably not surprised that Jira is our top pick for anybody looking for a scrum tool. It's not that it's such a great tool overall — something you can read about in our full Jira review — we can't argue against its usefulness as a scrum tool.

This is because Jira is a tailor-made Agile tool. The scrum board is built-in, and all the documentation is geared toward project managers comfortable with terminology like artifacts, epics and whatever else can be found in Agile handbooks. It makes the program rather impenetrable for everybody else, but scrum masters seem to love it.

2. Trello

Pricing: Free; cheapest plan costs \$5 per month (one-year plan)

Website: trello.com

Pros:

Great kanban board

Solid free plan

Great integrations

Cons:

May not be worth upgrading

Other features disappoint

A scrum board is in some ways a kanban board with a few tweaks, so if you don't like Jira you may want to check out Trello — the best kanban app out there. Though setting it up will take a little more effort than with Jira, if you want to focus on a smooth kanban experience, it may very well be worth it.

3. Wrike

Pricing: Free; cheapest plan costs \$9.80 per month (one-year plan)

Website: wrike.com

Pros:

Cheaper than most

Decent free plan

Cons:

Drab interface

Odd progression between plans

Wrike, an old-school project management tool that does a great job of managing scrum it just works really well. Each folder contains a full set of tools, and it's easy to jump between folders, which is great for scrum. Just make one folder for your backlog, another where you actively track issues, and that's a big part of the work done for you already. You can keep an eye on the big picture via the dash, which offers a great overview.

4. monday.com

Pricing: Free; cheapest plan costs \$8 per month (one-year plan)

Website: monday.com

Pros:

Lots of features

Plenty of great tools

User-friendly app

Cons:

Free plan is bad

Basic plan is worse

monday.com, the best project management software for small businesses, . This is mainly due to The monday.com menu which is the basis of the program - can be used as a backlog and run current issues via the kanban board, which is very good there are other options as well, but anyway you'll be able to work your way through the project.

5. Asana

Pricing: Free; cheapest plan costs \$10.99 per month (one-year plan)

Website: asana.com

Pros:

Excellent free version

Very user-friendly

Many different views

Cons:

Pricey

Big jump in price

Asana, an excellent project management suite. She often finds herself playing the second fiddle on monday.com, so check out our asana vs. monday.com comparison to learn more about that. This is because it is a bit more expensive than monday.com, but offers many of the same functionality.

This is certainly the case with the medium-term plan. The higher level is where Asana comes into its own. For all the details, we recommend you check out our Asana review, but what counts is that Asana is probably the best option for any company that plans well into the future, thanks to historical planning, advanced resource management, and a few other things. (digite magazine)

6. ClickUp:

Pricing: Free; cheapest plan per month costs \$5 (for one year)

Website: clickup.com

Pros:

- **Clean, sleek look**
- **options Simple pric**
- **for all core tasks is Great**

Cons:

- **Advanced tasks can be lacking**
- **Easy to lost detail**

ClickUp, a new tool in short we show that the program focuses more on(breadth rather than depth) , which makes it feel a little overstretched at times. Besides the boards and list, there are also some pretty innovative features , like a mind map (read our Taskade review for the only other tool we know of to have one of those) and a box view, which seems to be some form of org chart.

2.4.3. Crystal methodology

It is one of the ways that the Agile methodology can be applied in software development. At IBM's request, Alistair Cockburn (Alistair Cockburn) created it in 1991 to aid in the creation of object-oriented projects (object-oriented projects). In contrast to other methodologies, Kristal's technique primarily focuses on people and their interactions while working on a project. The Crystal methodology, like other ways to implement Agile, promotes early system delivery, the use of an iterative approach in development, the involvement of

the user or client throughout the work period, as well as flexibility and a reduction in bureaucracy.

Crystal methodology substitute

To accommodate teams of various sizes, Cockburn has created a collection of techniques or sub-methods, with each approach denoted by a distinct color. Usually, the size of the team and the significance of the project determine the best methodology to adopt. The categories of crystal methodology are

- **(Crystal Clear), where the work team comprises of no more than eight individuals.**
- **The work team for (Crystal Yellow) consists of 9–20 individuals.**
- **(Crystal Orange), which employs 21 to 50 people.**
- **(Crystal Orange Web), a team of 21–50 individuals focused on web initiatives.**
- **(Crystal Red), which employs between 51 and 100 individuals.**
- **(Crystal Maroon), which employs 101–200 individuals.**
- **Both (Crystal Diamond) and (Crystal Sapphire) are used in significant projects that could put human lives in danger. (Satyabrata_Jena)**

2.4.4. Extreme Programming (XP)

What is maximum XP programming or fast programming

Extreme programming ' XP is a lightweight, efficient, excellent, predictable, scientific and entertaining software for software production. In other words, MAXIMXP is programmed to meet the specific needs of software development by small teams in the face of vague and modified needs.

This is one of the methods of developing agile programs that provides values and principles to guide the behavior of the team and expects that the team will be organized. Express programming provides specific key actions to to:

Each exercise to achieve simple goals

A combination of practices to be a complex and emerging behavior

Figure (22) extreme program

Maximum XP programming includes writing unit tests before programming and maintaining all tests at all times. Unit tests are performed automatically and defects are quickly eliminated. So it reduces costs. On the other hand, you will start working with a simple design and size of the markup that has existing features and redesign if necessary. (Maleeha Arif Yasvi, 2019)

The coder is designed in pairs or pair format, with two coders on one page. While one is working, the other is constantly checking and providing input. Other important resources for this programming are:

- Mix and test the entire system several times a day

- **Introduce the working order into the production speed and upgrade at any time it is necessary**
- **Maintain customer consistency and get feedback**
- **Facilitate frequent changes consistent with software evolution by changing requirements**

The Agile management framework actually helps software development teams meet the needs of customers who may not know exactly what they want or whose needs change frequently.

QUSIXP software minimizes project management risks thanks to its adaptability to constantly changing needs. Just keep in mind that this principle involves a very small development team and close cooperation between managers and clients.

2.4.5. Dynamic Systems Development Method (DSDM)

The core values of SAFe outline the culture that leadership must promote and the behaviors that members of that culture should exhibit in order to effectively utilize the framework.

A. Format (Alignment)

SAFe mandates that organizations establish planning and thought rhythms at all organizational levels. With these components in place, everyone is aware of the company's current status, its objectives, and how everyone should work together to meet those objectives. All levels of the clipboard maintain consistency by routinely synchronizing people and activities. In contrast to conventional top-down command and control structures, information travels up and down in time.

B. Built-in quality

Agility should never be sacrificed for quality inside the SAFe architecture. Teams must specify what is meant by "done" for each job and project under SAFe, and they must integrate quality development techniques into each business agreement. The five key components of embedded quality, as defined by SAFe, are flow, architectural and design quality, code quality, system quality, and version quality.

C. Transparency

SAFe promotes behaviors that foster trust, such as organizing work in smaller group sizes so that issues can emerge sooner, offering real-time visibility of the backlog's progress across levels, and examining and changing rituals.

D. Program execution

The core of SAFe is program execution, which supports every other aspect of the framework. Teams and programs need to be able to consistently produce high-quality programs, work programs, and business value.

Leadership

Agile leadership conduct is required for SAFe leadership since only leaders can alter the system and establish the conditions for all fundamental values to be upheld.

*** Design and build the model: at this stage the product is designed and developed within iterative processes**

*** System implementation at the last stage, the system development is completed, the documentation is written, the review document is prepared, in addition to making sure that the system meets the customer's requirements, and then training users on how to use the system**

The team can use many effective tools in the development processes, such as the allocation of specific time intervals (Timeboxing), the Moscow prioritization method (Moscow Prioritization) and modeling (Prototyping)

Principles adopted in the method of developing dynamic systems the method of developing dynamic systems is applied based on eight basic issues

- **Focus on business needs**
- **On-time delivery**
- **Cooperation between the team and customers**
- **never can compromise on quality**
- **Progressive construction based on fixed foundations**
- **Iterative development**

Continuous and clear communication between team members and between teams and customers to show the Control

(Rodolfo Castello, 2004)

2.4.6. Feature Driven Development (FDD)

It is one of the methods that can be used to apply Agile methodology in software development. This methodology is focused primarily on customers and their requirements. It is a methodology known for short repetitions and repeated versions. By releasing new features frequently, developers are able to prioritize customer requirements, respond to those requirements in a timely manner, and maintain customer satisfaction. This methodology was developed by Jeff De Luca (Jeff De Luca) in 1997, while working in a team of 50 people on a banking project in Singapore. The feature-based development methodology is ideal for

large and complex projects in which large development teams work, which follow predefined standards and require fast releases. (S.R & Felsing,, 2002)

Steps of software development using the methodology of feature-based development

The software development process using the feature-based development methodology consists of five main steps, which begin after the stage of collecting information and requirements for the program or project:

*** Development of the overall model: the detailed outline of the project is being written at this stage. The problem that the client would like to find a solution to is determined, as well as the scope of the project is clearly and in detail defined.**

*** Create a list of features(Build a features list): so that a list of all the features or characteristics that the client wants to be available in the program is prepared. The process of developing any of these features should not exceed more than two weeks, and if it takes more time to develop them, they should be divided into smaller features.**

*** Planning depending on the feature (Plan by feature): at this stage, the order in which the features in the feature list will be developed and implemented will be determined.**

*** Design by feature: the lead programmer at this stage will determine which features will be designed and developed, will prioritize them, and the team that will be involved in the development of each feature.**

*** Feature-based implementation (Build by feature): at this stage, all the necessary elements are implemented to support the design of the feature, so that the user interface is designed, the design and testing of the prototype of the**

feature. If the feature successfully passes the test and is approved, this version can be added to the main version and made available to customers.

(Pavan Kumar, 2009)

2.4.7. Lean Software Development

Lean Software Development

Lean methodology for software development

lean methodology

Each software development methodology has its own features, and their life cycles are one of them. Many developers today would like to learn more about the software development life cycle using the lean methodology, in this article we will tell you about this methodology, but before doing this, it is necessary to find the appropriate definition of the lean methodology in software development.

Advantages of the lean methodology

Lean methodology has proven to improve software development in the following ways:

1-the methodology removes unnecessary process stages when designing the program so that it works as a time saver and simplifies the development process.

2-focusing on the Minimum Viable Product, The Lean methodology prioritizes basic functions so that this eliminates the risk of spending time on worthless constructions.

3-you increase the power of participation of your team as more and more members participate due to improving the overall workflow and reducing losses.

Basic principles of soft software development

There are several well-established principles that come with a set of tactics, practices and processes that build more efficient software products:

1-getting rid of waste

Identifying and eliminating waste in the project, for example unnecessary codes, delays in operations, inefficient communication, quality problem, data redundancy, more tasks in the log than completed ones, etc., project managers hold regular meetings. Which allows team members to clarify flaws and suggest changes in the next turn.

2. Fast Delivery

Long-time planning was previously the main success in the business, but over time it turned out that engineers spend a lot of time building complex systems with undesirable features. So they came up with a strategy (MVP i.e. minimal product) that resulted in quickly building products that included little functionality, launching the product on the market and seeing the reaction, this approach allowed them to promote the product based on customer feedback.

3-amplify learning

Learning is enhanced by ample code review, and meeting that can be applied across the team. It is also ensured that specific knowledge is not accumulated

by one engineer who writes a certain part of the code so that paired programming is used.

4. build quality

Lean's methodology is all about preventing waste, taking care not to sacrifice quality. Developers often apply “test-based programming ” to inspect code before writing it. Quality can also be gained from getting constant feedback from team members and project managers.

5-respect for teamwork

Lean methodology focuses on empowering team members, rather than controlling them. Such as creating a collaborative atmosphere, maintaining the perfect balance when there are short deadlines and a huge workload. This method becomes very important when new members join the team.

6. delay commitment

In traditional project management, it often happens when you submit your application and it turns out that it is completely unsuitable for the market. The lean methodology recognizes this threat and gives way to improvement by postponing irreversible decisions until all experiments are completed. This methodology always builds programs as flexible, so new knowledge is available and engineers can make improvements.

7. optimize the entire system

The principle of leniency allows managers to divide the problem into small parts to optimize the workflow of the team, create unity among members,

inspire them to a sense of shared responsibility leading to enhanced team performance.

2.2.8.Scaled Agile Framework (SAFe)

It is a set of organizational patterns and workflow patterns for implementing Agile methods at the enterprise level . A framework is a body of knowledge that includes structured guidance on roles and responsibilities, how to plan and manage work, and what values to support.

SAFe promotes alignment, collaboration and delivery across large numbers of Agile teams. It was formed around three basic knowledge bodies: agile software development, Lean Product Development, and systems thinking.

A structured method for agile scale growth is provided by SAFe when the amount of business increases. To accommodate varying levels of volume, SAFe offers four configurations: basic safe, large solution safe, wallet safe, and full safe.

In order to assist enterprises build better systems and software that better suit evolving consumer needs, Dean Leffingwell and Drew Jemilo introduced the SAFe program in 2011. Teams then delivered programs using conventional project management procedures. However, new frameworks have evolved to help businesses enhance the delivery of solutions throughout their organizations, and SAFe was born as a result of the growing requirement to react swiftly to changing market conditions. SAFe is one of the most widely used rapid delivery frameworks today, and its practitioners continue to improve it on a global scale.

Core values

The basic values of SAFe outline the culture that leadership must promote and the behaviors that members of that culture should exhibit in order to properly utilize the framework..

Conclusions	Search title	The researchers	
<p>: According to the study, software engineering's key field of agile development in cloud computing environments. There are numerous unresolved issues and gaps. More high-quality tools, research on evaluation, and empirical investigations are especially needed in this field.</p>	<p>Agile development in the cloud computing environment: A systematic review</p>	<p>Muhammad Younas Dayang N.A.Jawawi Imran Ghani TerrenceFries^c RafaqutKazmi^a</p>	١
<p>In this study, a framework is put out that shows how agile development in a cloud environment can be adopted. It explains every requirement for international agile development.</p> <p>The report also emphasizes the advantages of combining the agile software development technique with cloud computing. In the cloud context, this would effectively enable researchers and practitioners to perform</p>	<p>A Framework for Agile Development in Cloud Computing Environment</p>	<p>Muhammad Younas Imran Ghani Dayang N. A. Jawawi Muhammad Murad Khan</p>	٢

<p>worldwide agile software development.</p>			
<p>The purpose of this article was to demonstrate all the advantages of combining cloud computing and agile software development methodologies as a novel idea and a means of advancement. To demonstrate the elements that influence a firm's decision to move to a cloud computing solution, several resources and other aspects of the chosen company are evaluated. A case study of a warehouse management application is used to briefly introduce the DSDM approach and present the proposed cloud computing solution. The agile technique of software development is contrasted with the agile approach of software development that makes use of cloud computing. All benefits of the second strategy are mentioned. Cloud computing, or software that is distributed and utilized through a Web browser, can be said to be the direction of IT in the future.</p>	<p>Agile Software Development Using Cloud Computing: A Case Study</p>	<p>Muhammad Younas</p> <p>Dayang Norhayati Abang Jawawi</p> <p>Ahmad Kamil Mahmood</p> <p>Mohammad Nazir Ahmad</p>	<p>3</p>
<p>advantages of combining agile software development techniques with cloud computing as a novel idea and means to advance. To demonstrate the elements</p>	<p>Agile methods for cloud computing</p>	<p>Dzenana Donko</p> <p>S. Kalem</p> <p>Dusanka Boskovic</p>	<p>4</p>

<p>that influence a firm's decision to move to a cloud computing solution, several resources and other aspects of the chosen company are evaluated. The agile technique of software development is contrasted with the agile approach of software development that makes use of cloud computing. All benefits of the second strategy are mentioned. Cloud computing, or software that is distributed and utilized through a Web browser, can be said to be the direction of IT in the future. Agile software development methodologies enable attaining improved software quality and making frequent changes to software requirements easier by delivering and developing programs in this way.</p>			
<p>Agile software development methodologies are compact. Agile development methodologies are extremely practical in recognizing that In a corporate setting, the requirements are always changing. most knowledgeable individuals who are aware of the numerous</p>	<p>Agile Methodology Utilizing Cloud Computing</p>	<p>Aasima Sayeed1 Neelofar Hassan Mudasir Muttoo</p>	<p>5</p>

<p>Agile approach is being used in the creation of software to address issues with the conventional software management process. softwares. Numerous firms throughout the world use various agile techniques to their advantage. them</p>			
<p>The best outcomes are obtained when CLOUD COMPUTING is combined with AGILE DEVELOPMENT Methodologies. By developing software iteratively and getting immediate user feedback, AGILE DEVELOPMENT methodologies maximize the opportunities provided by CLOUD COMPUTING. The goal of this study is to emphasize the importance of CLOUD COMPUTING and AGILE DEVELOPMENT by fusing the two approaches together. Later, we create a cloud-based AGILE DEVELOPMENT Lifecycle that supports developers and aids in project management for software development. We conclude by extolling the virtues of AGILE CLOUD DEVELOPMENT, which aid in overcoming the difficulties of AGILE DEVELOPMENT and CLOUD COMPUTING.</p>	<p>Cloud Computing ensembles Agile Development Methodologies for Successful Project Development</p>	<p>Ambreen Nazir</p> <p>Ayesha Raana</p> <p>Muhammad Fahad Khan</p>	<p>6</p>

We think that AGILE CLOUD DEVELOPMENT is a huge promise for the IT industry because businesses enjoy using the services provided by both methodologies to make their projects distinctive and inventive.			
---	--	--	--

Chapter three:

Proposed research method

If you want to store your data to the cloud in fact you have a wide range to choose but the downside is that Google Microsoft Dropbox and the rest of the services are all controlled by someone other than you where if you want full control over your data and you have your own infrastructure to do it there are two of the biggest players

Doing your own cloud work can make sense for a number of reasons, one of which is cost, and often doing it yourself is cheaper than paying someone to do it for you assuming you have the ability to do it, which is a particularly big reason why I'm used to Windows Live Mesh to keep files syncing between different devices at home or work for free he always went online

We have to pay for cloud storage even if you don't want to store data online for other reasons you might want to host your own service it's control and flexibility If you have strict rules governing where your data can live this might be necessary for most people that won't stop them than using one of the major cloud vendors but still have more flexibility of running your own data rather than picking a one-size-fits-all solution - it all comes back to the particular example I have different machines syncing back to the server, and I also have some media services attached to that, so if you By dropping a file on the private server, it will be synchronized and made available for streaming to devices associated with the system or for authorized access via the cloud.

Using the self-hosted cloud is not only cheaper and faster than using OneDrive, but it also provides functionality that OneDrive can't.

other reasons you might want to security

Self-hosting means that your data or the services you provide are in your hands. On the other hand, when you purchase an external cloud service and you are not able for any reason to pay the fees, the seller will withhold the services it provides to you, and therefore the longing for any service within the cloud, meaning it is not like Google or Microsoft will fail if the subscriptions are not paid, not to mention the policies of countries that impose distrust In the event of uploading sensitive data to the paid cloud, which is managed by another country

now let's talk more about woncloud and nexcloud specifically both share the same original code base and both were founded by the same person there are some technical differences and this gap is likely to grow as the two projects diverge but a lot of the differences are more philosophical or licensing related if i quickly open the two platforms side by side you can see they share the same dna so why did the founder quit his own company and fork his own code to start a new company the own cloud company was formed by the partnership of open source developers with a venture capital firm fundamentally the problem stemmed from these two groups of people not seeing eye to eye i'm not going to go into in detail

Accessing data during work time to process it is a very important matter that must be characterized by speed and stability, and with many advantages of using the cloud, accessing data through it requires the Internet. This causes a problem.. Therefore, we have to think between merging the issue of using the

cloud with the possibility of data availability without the Internet, at least during the momentum of processing and the large number of orders

Here the idea of this research emerged, which presents an idea that many did not address, which is the use of the cloud inside Windows Server and Active Directory to take advantage of the Active Directory during work time and to access and process data through the cloud outside this time

3.1.Cloud migration

The process of migrating to the cloud involves moving applications, data, and digital files there. This process is similar to physical migration, with the exception that cloud migration involves moving applications, data, and its processes from one data center to another, rather than packing and shipping physical goods. (cloudflare, 2022)

Comparable to relocating to a larger office from a smaller one

Although moving to the cloud involves a lot of upfront planning and work, it is typically worthwhile because it can resulting in cost savings and increased flexibility.

The term "migration to the cloud" is most frequently used to describe the process of moving from local or legacy infrastructure to the cloud. If computer gear or software is out-of-date but is still in use, it is said to be "obsolete." By comparison to more contemporary options, outdated items and procedures are typically useless or unsafe. (Orban, 2022)

Puritanical businesses that operate antiquated systems run the risk of falling behind their rivals and facing a higher risk of data breaches.

Out-of-date software or hardware may become unreliable or slow, or the original vendor may stop providing support.

Servers, networking hardware, apps, databases, and any other hardware or software required for business operations are all included in the infrastructure. The commercial operations of the corporation could be slowed down by outdated infrastructure. The original vendors may stop supporting their products and stopping delivering security patches as it increases the security concerns.

The majority of legacy infrastructure is housed in structures, therefore it is actually situated on the grounds where the company conducts business. For instance, a lot of businesses house a local data center in the same building where their employees work.

Businesses that depend on regional legacy infrastructure are unable to take use of cloud computing. Because of this, the majority of businesses today have at least partially shifted to the cloud. (Zhao & Zhou, 2014)

3.2. Migrate large databases:

Big data is a huge amount of complex data that achieves high levels of distribution, huge quantum data sources, their speed is super and their diversity is great, and their size exceeds the speed of traditional computers and programs to store, process, and distribute them, and they are often available in their time, and take various forms if they are understood more deeply, and used better in the decision-making process (Thakar & Szalay, 2010)

For databases to operate in the cloud, they moved to a totally different platform. Moving a database is challenging, especially when there is a lot of data involved. For large databases that can take a while to transfer over the Internet, some cloud providers offer physical ways of data transfer, such transferring the data to a device before delivering the device to the cloud provider. Additionally, the Internet can be used to transport data. No matter the technique, data migration frequently takes a lengthy time.

A. Data consistency: After the data has been transferred, the next step is to confirm that it has been transferred securely and has not leaked.

B. Continuity of Operation: The company must make sure that its present systems are accessible and continue to function during the migration

process. To maintain service continuity, there will need to be some overlap between on-premises and the cloud. For instance, it is essential to make a copy of all data in the cloud before closing an existing database. In most cases, businesses must move incrementally rather than all at once. (Zhang, 2019)

3.3. migration from on-premises to the cloud work

Each work to be completed has different needs, and therefore the needs for migration to the cloud must be determined. Cloud service providers can also help the beneficiary established their migration procedure. These fundamental steps will be included in most cloud migrations.

A. Set goals:

Set goals helps the company measure whether the migration process is successful

B. Create a security strategy:

Comparing home security to cloud cybersecurity, a different strategy is needed. In the cloud, where the network essentially no longer exists and the company's data is no longer protected by a firewall.

when the installation of a web application firewall or cloud firewall may be required.

C. Copying data:

After selecting a cloud provider, copying data. Existing databases must be duplicated. To keep the cloud database current, continue doing this continuously throughout the migration process..

D. Business intelligence transfer:

This could entail reselling or rewriting the code. It can be completed all at once, gradually, or in stages. Moving production to the cloud from a structure

E. Immigration.

After completing these processes, some businesses choose to deactivate their local infrastructure, while others choose to retain older systems around as a backup or as part of a hybrid cloud deployment.. (RABETSKI , 2011) (Rabetski & Gerardo Schneider)

3.4. What is her accreditation The migration strategy to the cloud that organizations must

The highly regarded IT research firm Gartner lists five choices for businesses considering a cloud migration. These cloud migration techniques are referred to as the "5 R'S":

- A. Rehost-re-hosting is similar to the former but uses cloud servers. Employing this method, businesses will Recreate Their Application Architecture on a Laas infrastructure provider (as a service).**
- B. Refactor-companies that opt to rebuild will employ pre-existing frameworks and code, but will operate their applications on the PaaS platform provider's platform (as a service rather than re-registration).**
- C. Revision: This tactic entails expanding or partially rebuilding the code base. After that, grow them by repotting or rebuilding.**
- D. Rebuilding entails completely rewriting and redesigning the program on the Paas provider's platform; while this might be a labor-intensive procedure, it also allows developers to utilize contemporary capabilities from my vendors. PaaS**
- E. Replacement-Companies can also opt to completely abandon their outdated software and switch to SaaS applications that have already been developed by outside vendors. (cisco) (Perry, 2022)**

3.5. Which cloud deployment style should companies choose

Companies must decide on the cloud deployment strategy in addition to the cloud migration plan before beginning the migration.

A hybrid cloud combines two or more different types of settings, including local legacy data centers, private clouds, and public clouds. Integration between all deployed clouds and data centers must be tight for a hybrid cloud deployment to succeed, much as team members who are dispersed among various offices require constant contact.

Two or more public clouds are combined in a multi-cloud deployment. Numerous (different) clients share public clouds. Multicloud can, for instance, reduce expenses, take advantage of capabilities from two different cloud locations, and suit a variety of redundancy and backup needs.

Although it is not always possible for a corporation, deploying a single cloud from a single cloud resource is an alternative. Public and private clouds are both available from cloud companies; the difference is that private clouds are not shared with any other businesses. (Riley, 2021) (Tasneem, 2021)

3.6. The main challenges of migrating to the cloud

Large databases frequently need to move to a different platform in order to operate in the cloud. Moving a database is challenging, especially when there is a lot of data involved. For large databases that might take a while to transfer over the internet, some cloud service providers offer physical means of data transmission, such uploading data to a device and then charging the device to a cloud provider. Data can also be transferred via the internet. No matter the technique, data migration frequently takes a lengthy time.

A. Data integrity: the process of making sure that the transferred data is secure and safe once it has been transferred, and not leaked during the process.

- B. Continuous operation :** the business needs to ensure that its existing systems remain operational and available throughout the migration period. They will need some overlap between the premises and the cloud to ensure the
- C. continuity of the service :** for example, it is necessary to make a copy of all the data in the cloud before turning off an existing database. (R. Sahandi & Adel Alkhalil, 2013)

3.7. Now we have to choose the candidate tool to use to build the local cloud

3.7.1. Next Cloud

Nextcloud is a open and free source collaborative cloud software. It is a fork (derivative version) of ownCloud software. Cloud storage service, Nextcloud is invented by the founder of ownCloud. Unlike other popular services, with nextcloud you can configure your own storage system, on your server. Nextcloud gives you fine control over data access, facilitates file syncing, and enables sharing between devices. It is an excellent solution for not only private users but also for organizations. It supports multiple databases, like Oracle, SQLite, PosgreSQL, and MySQL. The project provides a desktop client for Windows, GNU/Linux and Mac OS, and a mobile app for apps and IOS. It also provides several additional features beyond storage. Cloud software allows you to place your data somewhere on the Internet so that it can be accessed from any Internet-connected device. Collaborative software or groupware or groupware is software that facilitates collaborative work by sharing documents, calendars, or contacts, by managing access groups, etc. Nextcloud is free, i.e. that it is license free. The investment relates to the rental or purchase

of the server to host it, its administration, and user support. All nextcloud components operate without exception under the free GNU AGPLv3 license. Indeed, a commercial license does not correspond to the philosophy of the developers. However, Nextcloud GmbH also offers paid professional support for Power users, which allows you to choose between three different models: Basic, Standard, and Premium. (ionos, 2022)

3.7.1.1. Features of next cloud

In terms of functionality nextcloud offers a wide range, which are: Synchronization of files between different computers, tablets and smartphones,

- A. Secure storage (encryption of files on the server, encryption of the connection of point-to-point), file sharing between nextcloud users and external users, calendar (allowing CalDAV synchronization), task management (synchronized with CalDAV), contact manager (CardDAV), online text editor (providing syntax highlighting) , online document viewer (PDF, OpenDocument); gallery**
- B. multi-format images (jpg, img, etc.), geographic location; note-taking taking into account supports Markdown, chat and video; ClamAV antivirus (optional) and many applications.**

Nextcloud offers a link to onlyoffice and collaborator online to allow joint editing Office documents (Libre Office and Microsoft Office). Unlike onlyoffice, collabora online consumes more resources. Making during its installation, some requests take too long to appear. Must also note that for online text editing, collaborator online can only accommodate about ten users, while onlyoffice can go up to 150 users.

C. In addition onlyoffice gives the full editor in the browser and processes each eventclient side then sends the results to the server.

This seems to offer an editing process much faster than a reverse approach. Onlyoffice uses OOXML as its base format which guarantees 100% compatibility with Microsoft Office files (.docx,.xlsx,.xlsx,.pptx).

D. Finally, onlyoffice offers a complete set of formatting tools and collaborative features for working on complex documents online.
(Nextcloud, 2022)

3.7.1.2. Advantages and disadvantages

A. Advantages: The interface design can be easily adapted to your own ideas and that at all moment. Protection against brute force attacks In addition to file sharing, the software brings various collaboration features like audio and video animations.

B. Disadvantages: Multifunctionality also increases the potential for errors and attacks

3.7.2. own Cloud

Own Cloud is an on-premise file sync and store solution that allows users to create their own cloud, manage services, permissions, and even provide hosting to other users. ownCloud is a cloud service that is secure, private and owned by the user himself. ownCloud solves the problem of remote access to confidential

files, by providing Universal File Access across devices running on almost all operating systems and containers. Most Cloud Platform Providers like Google Cloud Platform, Amazon Web Services, and the Microsoft Azure, provide paid enterprise versions that are packed with highly complex interfaces and features. ownCloud limits the complexity and makes user interface as simple as possible. It was born in 2010 to solve data privacy concerns. Unlike other cloud storage providers like Dropbox, who can monitor your stored data, ownCloud is based on the concept of build it yourself.

3.7.2.1. Applications ownCloud

is ideal for small scale applications. It has a highly modular and robust design, which makes it even compatible for large scale organisations. With numerous applications, the soul purpose of ownCloud is to provide a simple, easy to use yet powerful Cloud to users. A do it yourself project, that can be scaled to industry level as well. ownCloud can be used to provide remote access to confidential files, as well as sharing of files through a private medium. The software is configured using an IP address, that makes it private from outer world.

3.7.2.2. Benefits

The benefits of ownCloud are listed below:

- Private Cloud file storage system.
- Keeps file sync between all of your devices.
- Provides remote/ mobile access to all internal server files.
- Allows easy sharing of file with workers and coworkers.

- **Open-Source and free software.**
- **Cross-platform, provides integration of devices running on a variety of operating systems.**
- **Mobile application also supported.**
- **Simple front-end user interface.**
- **Easy privacy settings, visibility configurations, permissions, and security management.**
- **Modular design so that user can enable or disable capabilities according to the requirement.**
- **Custom settings supported along with plug-in application feature.**
- **ownCloud robust and scalable nature makes it available for teams of all sizes!**
- **Provides a Cloud that is managed by the user himself, which means maximum administrative power for user.**
- **Maximum privacy, no restrictions on stored content.**

ownCloud incorporates more than 10 million lines of code from 100,000 commits and more than 1000 contributors. ownCloud claims to have more than 10 million users. It has one of the largest open source community in the world.

More about ownCloud community

Compare and Contrast with its pros and cons with the existing commercial software for the same application. Below I provide a contrast between ownCloud and some of most successful commercial software.

Chapter four

Materials and method

4.1. using Agile method

In this chapter, we will build the agile model, where after we explained in previous chapters the types of cloud services, the benefits of the cloud server and the types of the agile model for building software, note that the practical side will be actually applied by the researcher for the benefit of the House of Wisdom Foundation in Iraq

Agile project management is an iterative and gradual work of organizing engineering and information technology activities and may enter into other areas of work. Being a very flexible and interactive methodology, this methodology enables teams to identify challenges, respond quickly, and at the end of the project deliver better results faster.

In this chapter, we will introduce eight agile project management templates.

4.2. Agile-Project-Plan

PROJECT NAME		PROJECT MANAGER	START DATE	END DATE	OVERALL PROGRESS			PROJECT DELIVERABLE	
model agile to add cloud to data		Hussam	1-1-2021	10-10-2022	20%			SCOPE STATEMENT	
AT RISK	TASK NAME	FEATURE TYPE	RESPONSIBLE	STORY POINTS	START	FINISH	DURATION (DAYS)	STATUS	COMMENTS
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sprint 1		hussam		9/2/22	9/13/22	10	Complete	
<input type="checkbox"/>	server installation		maher		9/2/22	9/7/22	4	Complete	
<input type="checkbox"/>	network installation		ahmed		9/7/22	9/12/22	5	Overdue	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Windows server install		hussam		9/9/22	9/13/22	4	In Progress	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sprint 2		hussam		9/16/22	9/24/22	8	Complete	
<input type="checkbox"/>	network installation		hussam		9/16/22	9/17/22	1	Complete	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Windows server tools		ahmed		9/17/22	9/21/22	4	Complete	
<input type="checkbox"/>	install ovmcloud		hussam		9/22/22	9/24/22	2	Not Started	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sprint 3		Shari W.		9/25/22	10/5/22	10	Complete	
<input type="checkbox"/>	install ovmcloud		hussam		9/25/22	9/29/22	4	Complete	
<input type="checkbox"/>	network test		ahmed		9/24/22	10/2/22	8	Complete	
<input type="checkbox"/>	data test		hussam & ahmed		10/2/22	10/5/22	3	complete	

4.3. Agile-Sprint-Backlog-Burndown-Chart

Scrum accumulation is the process of choosing the best components from the product accumulation and adding them to the speed race accumulation that was developed during speed planning. The work he moved to the development stage would be included in the enemy's accumulation. It is a list of tasks that must be accomplished in the current iteration, and it should be very definitive, thus no tasks should be added or removed.

Columns for the element Accumulation are present in this template.

4.4. Story points

- Responsibility**
- The case**
- And the original estimate.**

This is in the columns of the first day until the fifth day, where the number of additional hours required for development can be added each day to the task. In the total row at the bottom, the total amount of additional development hours per day for all missions in Enem is also shown. The breakdown diagram then represents this distinct action

4.4. Agile-Release-Plan

When there is no product to provide during race zero, the team may concentrate on setting a release target, adding features to be delivered, setting race features, and estimating the time required for each task. This is when rapid release planning takes place. The layout of the release may alter when new stories are added or removed.

You may put all of your jobs in this rapid release template, choose each item for a short race, and it will also determine the duration based on the start and end dates. When choosing a goal from the drop-down menu, the status of each task can also be indicated.

AGILE RELEASE PLAN TEMPLATE

AT RISK	SPRINT	TASK NAME	FEATURE TYPE	START	FINISH	DURATION	STATUS	RELEASE DATE
<input type="checkbox"/>	1	server installation	hardware	06/07/2022	08/07/2022	3	Released	12/07/2022
<input type="checkbox"/>	1	network installation	networking	12/07/2022	20/07/2022	8	Released	24/07/2022
<input type="checkbox"/>	1	os installation	software	19/07/2022	26/07/2022	7	Ongoing	01/08/2022
<input type="checkbox"/>	1	software installation	software	22/09/2022	29/09/2022	7	Planned	06/08/2022
<input type="checkbox"/>	1	test	testing	23/10/2022	30/10/2022	7	Ongoing	01/11/2022
<input type="checkbox"/>						0		

4.5. A strategic overview of the product's medium- and long-term orientation

It is provided by the agile roadmap. It establishes expectations inside your firm and directs the course of your product. Traditional roadmaps occasionally function as tight project plans, but in an agile workplace, a roadmap only offers direction and clarity.

Months or years can pass by on a product roadmap. For 2022, this template comprises Q2, Q3, and Q4

AGILE PRODUCT ROADMAP

4.6. Product backlog helps the product owner to follow the work of all the features that stakeholders want the product to include.

That is, the product build-up is somewhat similar to a wish list of all possible features in the finished product.

And unlike the accumulation of the enemy, the accumulation of the product can always change and improve. That is, anyone can add features to the product backlog, provided that priority is given to the product owner for each of them. The quick product build-up template includes drop-down columns for Story , ready-to-run and priority, status and story points and dedicated to the race. And it automatically calculates the total points for the story for each race based on the points of each mission.

AGILE PRODUCT BACKLOG TEMPLATE											
TASK ID	USER NAME	EPIC ID	ASSIGNED TO	START	END	STATUS	WIP	PRIORITY	STATUS	STORY POINTS	ASSIGNED TO EPIC
		Story 1	Person	2021-01-01		No	No	High	In Progress	20	No
Task 1				2021-01-01	2021-01-01	No	No	Medium	Complete	5	Yes
Task 2				2021-01-01	2021-01-01	No	No	Medium	Complete	10	Yes
Task 3				2021-01-01	2021-01-01	No	No	Medium	Complete	5	Yes
		Story 2									
		Story 3									
		Story 4									

Drop-down for Task 1, Story 1

Yes	High	Complete
No	Medium	In Progress
	Low	Not Started

4.9. Every project manager aims to produce a brief and straightforward project document, but many take months to prepare one that may contain thousands of words.

The Agile project document, on the other hand, is shorter and takes less time to create. A one-page, high-level, but detailed document serves as an agile project document. Its three main elements are devoted to the task, or the purpose for which the project was created, the project's vision (what will be accomplished in the project), and how the team should decide which projects have been finished.

PROJECT NAME	Adding cloud to data using agile
PROJECT CHAMPION	hussam
PROJECT SPONSOR	dr ALI PROMNDINA
PROJECT MANAGER	hussam
STAKEHOLDERS	House of Wisdom Foundation
EXPECTED START DATE	1/7/2022
EXPECTED COMPLETION DATE	1/11/2022

PROJECT DETAILS	
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	<p>Server hardware processing - - - communicate with the organization to determine the specifications</p> <p>Install the Windows Server 2019 System . The organization has been informed of the candidate version to make sure that there is no conflict with the software running on the server</p> <p>Completing the settings of the directrix shoulder</p> <p>Install nextcloud on the server because it will represent the cloud</p> <p>Operation and inspection</p>
AUTHORIZATION	Work authorizations and software are completed
OBJECTIVES	Increase the efficiency of data stored in a local server internally by delegating the shoulder directory and externally through the cloud
EXPECTED BENEFITS	Open access to data for processing or query from anywhere and at any time
SCOPE	Within the cloud environment
MILESTONES	Access to the cloud created from outside the local network
SUCCESS METRICS	Processing data without delay inside or outside the network
ESTIMATED COST & RESOURCES	The cost of the server and the license of the Windows OS
DATE	10/11/22

In the beginning, and in application of the agile system, an action plan was developed that boils down to

- 1- server hardware processing - - - communicate with the institution to determine the specifications**
- 2- install the Windows Server 2019 System . The organization has been informed of the candidate version to make sure that there is no conflict with the software running on the server**
- 3- complete the settings of DirecTV shoulders**
- 4- install nextcloud on the server because it will represent the cloud**
- 5- operation and inspection**

Communication with the beneficiary organization where a new dell type server with good specifications was provided the server was equipped with the windows server 2019 operating system

The images below show the work on the server and the researcher installing the Windows Server system

We will explain here the actual practical side after we explained in the previous chapters the types of cloud services, the benefits of the cloud server and the types of the Eagle model for building software, noting that the practical side will be actually applied by the researcher for the benefit of the House of Wisdom Foundation in Iraq

In the beginning, and in application of the agile system, an action plan was developed that boils down to

- server hardware processing - - - communicate with the institution to determine the specifications
- install the Windows Server 2019 System . The organization has been informed of the candidate version to make sure that there is no conflict with the software running on the server
- complete the settings of DirecTV shoulders
- installation owncloud on the server because it will represent the cloud
- operation and inspection

The beneficiary organization was contacted where a new dell type server with good specifications was provided the server was equipped with the windows server 2019 operating system

The images below show the work on the server and the researcher installing the Windows Server system

The photos below are for the implementation of item (I and II) of the action plan

ƴ -Here, the settings of the shoulder directory for the Windows Server have been completed, which was installed, and the local devices connected to the server within the organization have also been added

3

Ʒ -In the previous chapter, we learned about cloud tools and the importance of using a cloud owned by the beneficiary that guarantees us high-level security because data is stored inside the organization's servers, and in return, it is possible to access the servers and process data through the cloud, and it also ensures that the services provided do not stop if subscriptions are not paid

We will use the owncloud tool to start the settings directly on the server
First) adding a web matrix

↳-Log in to the owncloud website to download the tool

3-Open owncloud, define the database and add the participating files

-ξ open the owncloud tool, add the participating files and check the login

Conclusions

1. Using the public cloud has many benefits, the most important of which is the cost of resources does not fall on the shoulders of the beneficiary, but only the costs of purchasing the service

٢-in the public cloud, the development of resources is easy, it does not need to be equipped and transferred, but it is done through a relative increase in service fees

٣-cloud services companies have developed significantly after the corona wave as a result of the great orientation by organizations to cloud work

٤ - despite the attempts of private cloud computing companies to enhance trust between the consumer and the company, the barrier of confidentiality of consumer data still occupies a space of the latter's thinking

5-following the steps of migration to the cloud ensures that data is not lost and the service provided by the beneficiary is not interrupted for a long time

6-making a private cloud is easy if you have the resources

7-making a private cloud through the woncloud tool is more efficient because you do it yourself and it is also more secure if you consider that your data is managed only by you and there is no third party that can access it

8 the combination of the cloud and agile results in reliable software that meets the beneficiary's requests in the shortest possible time . It also promotes the spirit of teamwork

9-the kaniban board is one of the important methods of agile theories, as it encourages the team to have a spirit of cooperation and solve problems as soon as possible

10-the agile work schedules provided by the website make it easier for the data developer to use this theory significantly and it was used within this research

Recommendations

١-the use of the public cloud is an important thing that reduces the cost of establishing a data center for new companies, and Microsoft is considered \$ \$ \$ to be at the forefront of cloud computing companies this year ٢٠٢٢

2. In case your data is sensitive and confidential, in addition to having the necessary resources, owncloud and nextcloud tools allow you to manage your data yourself while providing cloud services.

الجماعي-teamwork is an important feature, especially when you use it with custom work theories for that

٤-the software developer should be familiar, even slightly, with networks and their work

3. References

4. HUSAINI, M. (n.d.). *MS 365 OFFICE FOR EDUCATION* .
5. Zhao, J.-F., & Zhou, J.-T. (2014). Strategies and Methods for Cloud Migration.
6. Abhishek, J., & Reena , R. (2011). *Analytical Study of Agile Methodology with Cloud Computing* .
7. Addicam.V.Sanjay. (2020). Overview of Agile Management & Development.
8. Amazon Cloud. (n.d.). Amazon Elastic Compute Cloud: User Guide for Linux Instances.
9. Ambreen, N., Ayesha, R., & ,Muhammad, F. (2013). Cloud Computing ensembles Agile Development Methodologies for Successful Project Development. *International Journal of Modern Education and Computer Science (IJMECS)*.
10. Azure website. (n.d.).
11. Azure website. (n.d.). <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/>.
12. berger, j. (n.d.). Citrix Cloud.
13. bluelock, b. (n.d.). <https://www.crunchbase.com/organization/bluelock>.
14. By Simplilearn, B. (2022). *What is Salesforce? The Ultimate Guide for 2023*.
15. cisco. (n.d.). <https://www.cisco.com/c/en/us/solutions/cloud/what-is-a-cloud-migration-strategy.html#~benefits>.
16. Citrix Product Documentation, C. (2022). Citrix DaaS.
17. cloudflare. (2022). What is cloud migration? | Cloud migration strategy. <https://www.cloudflare.com/en-gb/learning/cloud/what-is-cloud-migration/>.
18. digite magazine, d. (n.d.). *What Is Scrum Methodology? & Scrum Project Management*. https://www.digite.com/agile/scrum-methodology/?__cf_chl_captcha_tk__=63894cc024b2f8a7f7c208c0ae1ce9d483dc3aad-1625142913-0-AQxtsMr2ncnbtmM2p7JMCndFQvXhqQgSZYTO7dLpWmH_ul1sl2TLv_wUIXPpcn4_FbPk3Qn.
19. dynamics-microsoft. (n.d.). <https://dynamics.microsoft.com/en-us/>.
20. Haig-Smith, T., & Tanner, M. (2016). Cloud Computing as an Enabler of Agile Global Software Development.
21. ionos. (2022). ownCloud vs. Nextcloud: comparing cloud collaboration services. <https://www.ionos.co.uk/digitalguide/server/tools/owncloud-vs-nextcloud-a-comparison/>.
22. Jain1, A., & Abhishek, R. (2011). Analytical Study of Agile Methodology with Cloud Computing.
23. joyent-cloud. (n.d.). <https://www.joyent.com/>.

24. Kannan, N. (2012). 6 Ways the Cloud Enhances Agile Software Development.
25. Karlos Knox, K. (2021). *What is Google Cloud Platform (GCP)?*
26. Khalid , D., A Aljazeera, I., Th Salim, H., & Ali , H. (2021). Cloud Computing and its Impact on Online Education.
27. Langmead, B., & Nellore, A. (2018). Cloud Computing for Genomic Data Analysis and Collaboration.
28. Mahmood, Z., & Saeed, S. (n.d.). *Software Engineering Frameworks for the Cloud Computing Paradigm*. 2013.
29. Maleeha Arif Yasvi, M. (2019). Review On Extreme Programming-XP. *Conference: International Conference on Robotics, Smart Technology and Electronics EngineeringAt: Delhi*.
30. Microsoft. (n.d.). Microsoft Dynamics 365 2022 RELEASE WAVE 1 PLAN.
31. Nextcloud. (2022). Nextcloud User Manual The Nextcloud developers.
32. Orban, S. (2022). *"Migrating IT portfolios to the cloud is only the beginning of what is possible"*.
33. Pavan Kumar, P. (2009). Build Your Project Using Feature Driven Development.
34. Perry, Y. (2022). What is Cloud Migration? Strategy, Process and Tools.
35. R. Sahandi, R., & Adel Alkhalil, A. (2013). Migration to Cloud Computing- The Impact on IT Management and Security.
36. RABETSKI , P. (2011). Migration of an on-premise application to the Cloud.
37. Rabetski, P., & Gerardo Schneider. (n.d.). Migration of an on-premise application to the Cloud: Experience repor.
38. Rackspace . (n.d.). *Rackspace Technology Recognized as a Leader in 2022 ISG Provider Lens™ Next-Gen Private/Hybrid Cloud – Data Center Services & Solutions Report in Managed Hosting & Managed Services for the U.S. Public Sector*.
39. rackspace. (n.d.). <http://www.onestopcomm.com/carrier/rackspace/>.
40. Rash, W. (2018). IBM Cloud Review.
41. release wave 1 plan. (n.d.). <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/dynamics365-release-plan/2022wave1/>.
42. Riley, N. (2021). Which cloud deployment model is right for your business?
43. Rodolfo Castello, R. (2004). Maleeha Arif Yasvi Development of Software Industrial Projects and Their Impact in the Academic Environment.
44. S.R, P., & Felsing,, M. (2002). Practical Guide to Feature-Driven Development.
45. Sarangam, A. (2021). *8 Important Types Of Agile Methodology (2022)*.

46. Sarangam, A. (2022). *Important Types Of Agile Methodology (2022)*.
47. Satyabrata_Jena, S. (n.d.). *Crystal methods in Agile Development/Framework*.
48. Sharda, R., & Delen, D. (2020). *Deep Learning and Cognitive Computing* 315.
49. Sharma, M. (n.d.). *CLOUD COMPUTING*. Lovely Professional University.
50. Snider, M. (2021). *Verizon brings unlimited storage to cloud data battle with Apple, Amazon and Google*.
51. Tasneem, S. (2021). *How To Choose The Right Cloud Deployment Model For Your Organization?*
52. Thakar, A., & Szalay, A. (2010). *Migrating a (large) science database to the cloud*.
53. verizon-cloud, v.-c. (n.d.). <https://www.verizon.com/solutions-and-services/verizon-cloud/>.
54. Wang, X., & Durowoju, O. (2011). *The impact of security and scalability of cloud service on supply chain performance*.
55. wikipedia, w. (n.d.). https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Citrix_Cloud.
56. Zhang, P. (2019). *Practical Guide to Large Database Migration*.

THE END